

SYNTHESIS OF SUBSTITUTED DINITRO PHENYLKETONES AND PHENYLACETIC ACIDS. PART III.

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2:4-Dinitro-6-iodophenylacetone and 2:4-dinitro-6-iodophenylacetic acid have been prepared by the ketonic and acid hydrolysis, respectively, of 2:4-dinitro-6-iodophenylacetoacetic ester. 2-Methyl-3-ethylcarboxy-5-iodo-7-aminoindole has been obtained by the reduction of the above mentioned ester with iron powder and water.

In the previous communications of this series (this *Journal*, 1947, 24, 268, 374) it has been shown that 1-chloro-2:6-dinitro-4-bromobenzene and 1-chloro-2:4-dinitro-6-bromobenzene condense easily with acetoacetic and malonic esters in absolute ether, and the condensation products, so obtained, yield the respective dinitrobromophenylacetic acids and acetones on hydrolysis with alkali and acid respectively.

In this paper this reaction has been extended to 1-chloro-2:4-dinitro-6-iodobenzene.

EXPERIMENTAL

2:4-Dinitro-6-iodophenol was prepared previously by Armstrong (*Ber.*, 1873, 6, 651) by the iodination of 2:4-dinitrophenol, but the exact experimental details are not available. It was therefore prepared by dissolving 2:4-dinitrophenol (36.8 g.) in hot glacial acetic acid and adding to it gradually a finely powdered mixture of iodine (40.8 g.) and freshly precipitated yellow mercuric oxide (21.7 g.) during the course of 6 hours. Each addition of the mixture was followed by heating to boiling and stirring by a mechanical stirrer till the colour of the iodine was discharged. Afterwards, it was finally stirred for an hour and the precipitated mercuric iodide allowed to settle down. The acetic acid layer was decanted off and diluted with water; the reddish yellow product was filtered and recrystallised from hot alcohol when fine yellow needles were obtained, m.p. 102°, yield 42 g. A further quantity (12 g.) was obtained from the filtrate by removal of the alcohol, yield 87.1% of theory. One more recrystallisation raised the melting point to 106° (cf. Armstrong, *loc. cit.*), but for the preparation of the chlorodinitroiodobenzene this is not necessary.

1-Chloro-2:4-dinitro-6-iodobenzene was prepared from 2:4-dinitro-6-iodophenol (40 g.), *p*-toluene sulphonyl chloride (27.4 g.) and diethylaniline (20 c.c.) by the method of Joshi and Sane (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 9, 60) with a slight modification. The mixture, after heating on a water-bath for 4 hours, was treated with dilute hydrochloric acid, when an oil separated out. The hydrochloric acid layer was decanted off and the oil treated with a small quantity of alcohol when in a short time it solidified. On filtration the chloro compound was obtained in the form of greenish yellow needles, m.p. 102°, yield 30 g. (70.8% of theory). Recrystallisation from hot alcohol raised the melting point to 106° (cf. Armstrong, *loc. cit.*); for condensation with acetoacetic ester the crude product was used.

4-Dinitro-6-iodophenylacetoacetic Ester.—The sodium derivative of ethyl acetoacetate was prepared from 20.8 g. of ethyl acetoacetate and 317 g. of sodium in 40 c.c. of ether. When the last traces of sodium had disappeared, the solution was cooled in ice and 1-chloro-2 : 4-dinitro-6-iodobenzene (26.4 g.) was added. The mixture was refluxed for 6 hours and then left overnight. It was extracted first with water (300 c.c. approx.) and then with equal amount of 2% caustic soda solution, and the combined extracts acidified with dilute nitric acid, when a dark coloured oil separated out. After standing overnight in a refrigerator, the supernatant aqueous layer was decanted off, the oil dissolved in cold alcohol and the alcoholic solution allowed to evaporate slowly, when the ester crystallised out as dark coloured plates. Crops were collected after a week, but after about 19 g. had been collected, further evaporation of the alcoholic solution yielded only an oil. Recrystallisation was effected by dissolving in cold alcohol, filtering, and allowing it to evaporate by itself, when dark reddish brown crystals of the ester were obtained, m.p. 74°, yield 57.4% of theory. (Found : N, 6.80. $C_{12}H_{11}O_7N_2I$ requires N, 6.61 per cent).

The reaction was also carried out in anhydrous benzene instead of ether, and the same yield of the ester was obtained.

2 : 4-Dinitro-6-iodophenylacetone.—The finely powdered crude ester (5.8 g.) was dissolved in concentrated sulphuric acid (51 c.c.) and water (24 c.c.) added without cooling. After the evolution of carbon dioxide had ceased, the dark solution was poured on crushed ice, allowed to stand in a refrigerator for 2 days and then filtered. The product was dissolved in hot alcohol, filtered and the filtrate allowed to evaporate slowly, when the ketone crystallised out as dark coloured needles, m.p. 110°, yield 4 g. (83.1% of theory). (Found : N, 8.11. $C_8H_5O_2N_2I$ requires N, 8.0 per cent).

The *phenylhydrazone* was prepared by dissolving the above ketone (1 g.) in the minimum quantity of alcohol and adding to it about 1.5 c.c. of phenylhydrazine. The mixture was refluxed for half an hour and then cooled. The phenylhydrazone separating was filtered and recrystallised from hot alcohol as light, fine red flakes, m.p. 74° (decomp.), yield 1.0 g. (79.6% of theory). (Found : N, 12.91. $C_{10}H_{13}O_2N_3I$ requires N, 12.73 per cent).

The *oxime* was obtained by dissolving the above ketone (1.2 g.) in alcohol and adding to it hydroxylamine hydrochloride (0.6 g.) followed by caustic soda solution, till it turned just alkaline to phenolphthalein. After refluxing the mixture for an hour, the contents were poured in 100 c.c. of water, allowed to stand for 2 days in a refrigerator and then filtered. The dark coloured product was dissolved in hot alcohol, filtered, and the filtrate allowed to evaporate, when the oxime crystallised out as fine needles, m.p. 75°, yield 0.8 g. (64% of theory). (Found : N, 11.07. $C_8H_9O_2N_2I$ requires N, 11.38 per cent).

2 : 4-Dinitro-6-iodophenylacetic Acid.—The crude 2 : 4-dinitro-6-iodophenylacetoacetic ester (3 g.) was refluxed for half an hour with 15 c.c. of 20% alcoholic potash to which 1 c.c. of water had been added. The alcohol was then distilled off, the residue acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid, left overnight and then filtered. The filtrate was allowed to evaporate slowly when the acid crystallised out as a dark brown powder.

It does not melt, but on heating strongly gives off iodine. It dissolves in sodium bicarbonate solution with effervescence and is reprecipitated by hydrochloric acid as a brown powder, confirming that it is an acid; yield 2 g. (80% of theory). (Found: N, 7.58. $C_8H_8O_6N_2I$ requires N, 7.95 per cent).

2-Methyl-3-carboxyethyl-5-iodo-7-aminoindole.—The crude 2:4-dinitro-6-iodo-phenylacetoacetic ester (2 g.), iron powder (3 g.), crystallised ferrous sulphate (0.3 g.) and water (10 c.c.) were refluxed for 3 hours and then cooled in ice-water with constant shaking. After filtration, the residue was boiled with alcohol (20 c.c.) and animal charcoal and the extract filtered hot. The filtrate was allowed to evaporate slowly, when the cyclised amine crystallised out as a colourless solid, which turned black immediately on exposure to atmosphere, m.p. 135° (decomp.), yield 1.2 g. (73.6% of theory). (Found: N, 8.25. $C_{12}H_{13}O_2N_2I$ requires N, 8.14 per cent).

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